

Open Search for Science - Science for Open Search

S. Voigt[†] and T. Hecking, Dennis Jankowski and Maximilian Schwinger,
German Aerospace Center,
Oberpfaffenhofen/Cologne/Oldenburg, Germany

Abstract

Science is about the discovery of new things, knowledge, concepts, contexts, systematics, relations etc. The more data and information we render and collect in the digital sphere and use as the basis for science, the more important it is to ensure open, unbiased and public access to it. Science has a vital role in and responsibility for this. It profits significantly from the ease of exchange of data and information and thus also has a responsibility in keeping it open, accessible, findable and curated.

Large scientific organisations consume large quantities of information and data from external sources into their research environments. They generate, store, manage and maintain large amounts of information in their intranet, research systems, data repositories and information corpora as well as they generate large volumes of scientific artefacts which they output to the public domain. The German Aerospace Centre, with a bit less than 10.000 scientific, technical and administrative staff has a vital interest in ensuring that access to digital information is unbiased, objective and as efficient as possible. Internally, within the organisation, as well as externally, in the web. The thus established ‘OpenSearch@DLR’ project is currently in its second year and in this talk we present first findings, approaches and lessons learnt from the project as well as we demonstrate pilot applications for scientific search.

During the course of the project we also found the following: Efficient searching and finding of information within the different repositories of the organisation is as important as searching for external resources on the web. In particular for scientists, finding and retrieval of research data is very important and needs better technical tools and support. This requires thematically pre-structured and pre-processed information on existing data and information to better search in internal repositories and corpora. Often enough, information needs to be found in heterogeneous artefacts (such as papers, software tools, manuscripts, etc.) which are often distributed over various different subsystems. Techniques for automatic content analysis have to be advanced to identify relationships between scattered pieces of information and data, which enable integrated search and discovery of scientific knowledge simultaneously and synergistically across different repositories and corpora: e.g. to search for authors, scientific concepts, tools or techniques. To this end, representing extracted information and resources as well as semantic relations between them in graph-databases seems to be a promising approach for this.

Sophisticated search involves efficient visualisation and analysis tools, allowing deeper insight in to search results and going far beyond of what is offered in today's standard search tools. This includes for example that the availability and analysis capabilities of geospatial search features need to be significantly improved for all kinds of search and analysis tasks in the web. Along with this, time-stamps and versioning of web artefacts are equally important factors. Versions of knowledge artefacts have to be tracked in order to avoid inconsistencies and ensure that data of known provenance and up-to-date-ness are used for scientific analysis. Furthermore, there is a need for the identification of emerging topics and to anticipate future trends of scientific and technological or even societal developments.

All in all, it can be established that good internal search features, good internal knowledge management and thus, sophisticated intranet search is a critical infrastructure for science centres, which need better care and which by far should not be considered a by-product. In conclusion we argue that improving the intranet search features and linking them with sound public and distributed open web search infrastructures will substantially improve the scientific work and organizational efficiency of many large-scale science organizations. Thus, many major science and research organisation need to actively engage in the building and maintaining of openly searchable information repositories internally, as well as where possible, also externally, in cooperation with others and for searching the web as a whole.